

1 **Appendix I: short description of the datasets mobilised through the MICA project**

3 *Muskrat captures in Flanders, Belgium*

4 Muskrat captures in Flanders, Belgium is an occurrence dataset published by the Research
5 Institute for Nature and Forest (INBO). It contains information on all officially registered
6 captures of muskrat (*Ondatra zibethicus*) in and around Flanders, Belgium between 1991 and
7 2018. These data are provided by different management actors: the Flanders Environment
8 Agency (VMM), Rattenbestrijding Oost-Vlaanderen (RATO vzw), Polders and Wateringen
9 (vvpw), and provincial and municipal trappers, and aggregated and analysed by the INBO
10 since 1991. Here it is published as a standardised Darwin Core Archive and includes for each
11 occurrence record an occurrenceID, date, location, samplingProtocol (trap) and
12 samplingEffort (number of days or traps), scientific name, and the organisation who made the
13 capture. The original dataset contains close to 450.000 occurrences and is available on
14 GitHub, but only presence records (over 103.000) are included in this version, which can be
15 used to track muskrat distribution in Flanders since 1991.

17 This dataset can be considered as the 'legacy' dataset for Flanders. This Historical data was
18 initially aggregated from official registered captures from various sources in Flanders to
19 follow up catches and autopsy data of Muskrat in Flanders
20 (<https://github.com/inbo/muskusratten>). It was published on GBIF through MICA. The data
21 publication steps and scripts are available here: [https://github.com/inbo/mica-
22 occurrences/tree/master/datasets/mica-legacy-occurrences](https://github.com/inbo/mica-occurrences/tree/master/datasets/mica-legacy-occurrences)

24 The legacy dataset is a non living dataset, therefore it was only published once.

26 Method step description:

- 27 1. Source data are submitted by the different management actors on either a monthly or
28 yearly basis. Initially these submissions were done by mailing the monthly numbers
29 which were then digitised in Excel spreadsheet. Since the early 2000s all management
30 actors have switched to submitting their catches in Excel spreadsheets.
- 31 2. A csv export of the master Excel spreadsheet was uploaded to a GitHub repository
32 (<https://github.com/inbo/muskrat-occurrences>).
- 33 3. We developed a RMarkdown script to document and perform the transformation of the
34 data to Darwin Core, which includes the following steps:
 - 35 a. Perform some basic data cleaning of the raw data.
 - 36 b. Create an occurrence core file ([http://rs.gbif.org/core/dwc_occurrence_2015-
37 07-02.xml](http://rs.gbif.org/core/dwc_occurrence_2015-07-02.xml)) for presence-only and all data.
- 38 4. The presence-only Darwin Core data file is uploaded to the INBO IPT (Robertson et
39 al. 2014) and documented with metadata.
- 40 5. The dataset is published and registered with GBIF.

42 *VMM - Rat control occurrences in Flanders, Belgium*

43 The "VMM - Rat control occurrences in Flanders, Belgium" dataset is an occurrence dataset
44 published by Flanders Environment Agency (VMM). The dataset is assembled by the VMM
45 to monitor and control pest organisms in Flanders from 2016 onwards. It mainly includes
46 observations of muskrats and brown rats, but other animal and plant pest species are included
47 as well. Here it is published as a standardised Darwin Core Archive and includes for each
48 occurrence record: an occurrenceID, scientific name, number of individuals (optional), date
49 and location.

50

51 This dataset provides up to date data in an automatic workflow and is published and updated
52 weekly.

53

54 Method step description:

- 55 1. The source data for this standardised dataset is managed by the Flanders Environment
56 Agency (VMM).
- 57 2. An SQL script was developed to transform the data to Darwin Core. This mapping
58 script was uploaded to a GitHub repository [https://github.com/riparias/vmm-rattenapp-](https://github.com/riparias/vmm-rattenapp-occurrences/tree/main/sql)
59 [occurrences/tree/main/sql](https://github.com/riparias/vmm-rattenapp-occurrences/tree/main/sql) and includes the following steps:
 - 60 a. Perform some basic data cleaning of the raw data.
 - 61 b. Generate stable and unique identifiers for each occurrence (occurrenceID).
 - 62 c. Create an occurrence core file ([https://rs.gbif.org/core/dwc_occurrence_2022-](https://rs.gbif.org/core/dwc_occurrence_2022-02-02.xml)
63 [02-02.xml](https://rs.gbif.org/core/dwc_occurrence_2022-02-02.xml)).

64

65 *MICA - Muskrat occurrences collected by VMM in Flanders, Belgium*

66 MICA - Muskrat occurrences collected by VMM in Flanders, Belgium is an occurrence
67 dataset published by the Flanders Environment Agency (VMM). It is part of the LIFE project
68 MICA, in which innovative techniques are tested for a more efficient control of muskrat and
69 coypu populations, both invasive species. This dataset contains mainly muskrat and brown rat
70 catches. Here it is published as a standardised Darwin Core Archive and includes for each
71 occurrence record an occurrenceID, date, location, sampling protocol, the number of recorded
72 individuals, status (present/absent) and scientific name.

73

74 This dataset provides up to date data in a semi-automatic workflow and is published and
75 updated when appropriate.

76

77 Method step description:

- 78 1. Data are collected in the field by specialised trappers, using the predefined sampling
79 protocol.
- 80 2. An R script script is created to map the original data to Darwin Core.
- 81 3. The resulting Darwin Core data files are uploaded to the INBO IPT and documented
82 with metadata.
- 83 4. The dataset is published and registered with GBIF.

84

85 *MICA - Muskrat, Raccoon and Coypu occurrences collected by ITAW in Germany*

86 MICA - Muskrat and Coypu and Raccoon Occurrences collected by ITAW, Germany is an
87 occurrence dataset published by the Research Institute of Nature and Forest (INBO) and
88 ITAW (Institute for Terrestrial and Aquatic Wildlife Research). It is part of the LIFE MICA -
89 Management of Invasive Coypu and Muskrat in Europe project on Muskrat monitoring
90 networks in Flanders, The Netherlands and Germany. This dataset contains Muskrat, Raccoon
91 and Coypu counts. Here it is published as a standardised Darwin Core Archive and includes
92 for each occurrence record an recordID, date, location, samplingProtocol, the number of
93 recorded individuals, status (present/absent) and scientific name.

94

95 This dataset provides up to date data in a semi-automatic workflow and is published and
96 updated when appropriate.

97

98 Method step description:

- 99 1. Data are collected in the field by specialised trappers and recorded in a Google sheet.

- 100 2. An R script script is created to map the original data to Darwin Core as occurrence
101 Core.
- 102 3. The Darwin Core text file (occurrence.txt) is uploaded in the INBO IPT and
103 documented with metadata.
- 104 4. The dataset is published and registered with GBIF.
105

106 *MICA - Muskrat and coypu occurrences collected by UVW in the Netherlands*

107 MICA - Muskrat and coypu occurrences collected by UVW in the Netherlands is an
108 occurrence dataset published by the Research Institute of Nature and Forest (INBO) and the
109 Netherlands Biodiversity Information Facility (NLBIF). It is part of the LIFE project MICA,
110 in which innovative techniques are tested for a more efficient control of muskrat and coypu
111 populations, both invasive species. This dataset contains muskrat and coypu counts. Here it is
112 published as a standardized Darwin Core Archive and includes for each occurrence record an
113 occurrenceID, date, location, the number of recorded individuals, status (present/absent) and
114 scientific name.
115

116 This dataset provides up to date data in a semi-automatic workflow and is published and
117 updated every 3 months.
118

119 Method step description:

- 120 1. Data are collected in the field by specialized trappers, using the predefined sampling
121 protocol.
- 122 2. An R script script is created to map the original data to Darwin Core as occurrence
123 Core.
- 124 3. The Darwin Core text file (occurrence.txt) is uploaded in the NLBIF IPT and
125 documented with metadata.
- 126 4. The dataset is published and registered with GBIF.
127

128 *Muskrat trapping data in the Netherlands 1987 – 2014*

129 Muskrat trapping data in the Netherlands 1987 – 2014 is an occurrence dataset published by
130 het Waterschapshuis and the Netherlands Biodiversity Information Facility (NLBIF). Trapped
131 muskrats in the Netherlands have been manually registered at municipal and provincial level
132 since 1941, from 1987 they have been registered on atlas blocks (5 x 5 km) and from 2014
133 this is done with a smartphone at the trap location. The years of registration have yielded a
134 valuable dataset that has been used in multiple studies.
135

136 The legacy dataset is a non-living dataset, therefore it was only published once.
137

138 Method step description:

- 139 1. Data are collected in the field by specialised trappers, using the predefined sampling
140 protocol.
- 141 2. Data from 1987-2014 are registered in atlas blocks (5 x 5 km). All data are aggregated
142 in 13 four-weeks' time periods each year and entered in an Excel spreadsheet.
- 143 3. An R script script is created to transform the original data structure into a single
144 occurrence format with one value per time period per atlas block each year. Only
145 values for atlas blocks with a number for trapped muskrats remained (299K records
146 i.e. 64% of all records).
- 147 4. In R geographic coordinates and accuracy are added, based on atlas block indexes, and
148 the time periods are to be rewritten into an eventDate format with a begin and an end
149 date.

150 5. The output is a DarwinCore occurrence file, which is uploaded via the NLBIF IPT and
151 documented with metadata.

152

153 *RATO - daily operations commissioned by the province East Flanders, Belgium*

154 The RATO - daily operations commissioned by the Province East Flanders, Belgium dataset is
155 an event dataset published by RATO. The dataset includes data on management actions on
156 invasive alien species and nuisance species, predominantly in the province of East Flanders
157 and from 2021 onwards. Here it is published as a standardised Darwin Core Archive and
158 includes for each occurrence record an occurrenceID, date, location, scientific name, sampling
159 protocol, sampling effort and the number of recorded individuals or biomass.

160

161 This dataset provides up to date data in an automatic workflow and is published and updated
162 weekly.

163

164 Method step description:

- 165 1. A WFS export of the database was generated by RATO and uploaded to a GitHub
166 repository (<https://github.com/riparias/rato-occurrences/tree/master/data/raw>).
- 167 2. We developed a Rmarkdown script to document and perform the transformation of the
168 data to Darwin Core, which includes the following steps:
 - 169 a. Perform some basic data cleaning of the raw data.
 - 170 b. Create an occurrence core file (http://rs.gbif.org/core/dwc_occurrence_2015-07-02.xml)
- 171 3. The Darwin Core data file is uploaded to the INBO IPT and documented with
172 metadata.
- 173 4. The dataset is published and registered with GBIF.

174

175 *MICA - Muskrat occurrences collected by RATO in East Flanders, Belgium*

176 MICA - Muskrat occurrences collected by RATO in East Flanders, Belgium is an occurrence
177 dataset published by the Research Institute of Nature and Forest (INBO). It is part of the LIFE
178 project MICA, in which innovative techniques are tested for a more efficient control of
179 muskrat and coypu populations, both invasive species. This dataset contains muskrat trap
180 captures. Here it is published as a standardised Darwin Core Archive and includes for each
181 occurrence record an occurrenceID, date, location, the number of recorded individuals, status
182 (present/absent) and scientific name.

183

184 The legacy dataset is a non living dataset, therefore it was only published once.

185

186 Method step description:

- 187 1. Source data are submitted by the different management actors on either a monthly or
188 yearly basis. Initially these submissions were done by mailing the monthly numbers
189 which were then digitised in Excel spreadsheet. Since the early 2000s all management
190 actors have switched to submitting their catches in Excel spreadsheets.
- 191 2. A csv export of the master Excel spreadsheet was uploaded to a GitHub repository
192 (<https://github.com/inbo/muskrat-occurrences>).
- 193 3. We developed a Rmarkdown script to document and perform the transformation of the
194 data to Darwin Core, which includes the following steps:
 - 195 a. Perform some basic data cleaning of the raw data.
 - 196 b. Create an occurrence core file (http://rs.gbif.org/core/dwc_occurrence_2015-07-02.xml) for presence-only and all data.

197

198

- 199 4. The Darwin Core data file is uploaded to the INBO IPT and documented with
200 metadata.
201 5. The dataset is published and registered with GBIF.
202

203 *MICA - Muskrat and coypu camera trap observations in Belgium, the Netherlands and*
204 *Germany*

205 MICA - Muskrat and coypu camera trap observations in Belgium, the Netherlands and
206 Germany is an occurrence dataset published by the Research Institute of Nature and Forest
207 (INBO). It is part of the LIFE project MICA, in which innovative techniques are tested for a
208 more efficient control of muskrat and coypu populations, both invasive species. The dataset
209 contains camera trap observations of muskrat and coypu, as well as many other observed
210 species.
211

212 Method step description:

- 213 1. Cameras were placed in MICA project areas according to [this protocol](#).
214 2. Images were annotated both manually and by the Agouti AI. The occurrences derived
215 from the images were exported from Agouti.
216 3. An R script is created to map the original data to Darwin Core as occurrence Core.
217 4. The dataset is published and registered with GBIF.
218